

*Seong-Gun Bae^{1†}, Yoonjoo Lee², and Dong-Geun Shin^{1†}

¹Aerospace & Convergence Materials Center, Korea Institute of Ceramic Engineering & Technology, Jinju 52851, Republic of Korea

²Semiconductor Materials Center, Korea Institute of Ceramic Engineering & Technology, Jinju 52851, Republic of Korea

† Corresponding author: sg0329@kicet.re.kr, dgshin73@kicet.re.kr

Introduction

✓ Polycarbosilane

- Si-C backbone structure
- major intermolecular bonding : Si-CH₃, Si-CH₂, Si-C, Si-H
- C/Si ratio : 2 (carbon excess structure)

✓ Silicon carbide fiber

- Reinforcement of Ceramic matrix composites(CMCs)
- Excellent physical & chemical properties
- Applications : aerospace, nuclear, military

✓ Microstructure of SiC-HfC Nanocomposite fiber

✓ Expected effect of hafnium carbide

✓ Carbon control by intermediate oxidation

Experiment / Results & Discussion

Experiment

✓ Fabrication process of SiC-HfC nanocomposite fibers

Sample	Oxidation curing	Pyrolysis condition	Intermediate oxidation	Sintering condition
SiC-HfC1				1800 °C/Ar
SiC-HfC2	200 °C / Air	1600 °C/Ar	700 °C / Air	1800 °C/Ar
SiC-HfC3				2000 °C/Ar

- Near-stoichiometric SiC-HfC nanocomposite fibers were fabricated using Al-Hf modified polycarbosilane

Microstructure

✓ Field Emission – Scanning Electron Microscopy

- FE-SEM (JEOL-JSM7610E, JEOL, Japan) operating condition: accelerate Voltage 30kV, current charge 30uA / Secondary Electron Imaging (SEI), Back scattered electron imaging (BSE) mode

Phase & Carbon analysis

✓ X-ray Diffraction

Samples	Phase analysis	Crystallite size, D (nm) SiC (111)	Crystallite size, D (nm) HfC (111)	I ₁₁₁ /I ₀
SiC-HfC1	Carbon 3C-SiC HfC	21.4	18.2	0.63
SiC-HfC2	3C-SiC HfC	23.8	22.3	0.39
SiC-HfC3	3C-SiC HfC	93.2	48.8	1.28

- XRD (D8Advance, Bruker, USA) operating condition : CuK_α, 0.02° step, 2θ-80°, 0.02° step, scan time 0.4s
- Raman Spectroscopy (LabRAM ARAMIS, Horiba Jobin Yvon, France) operating condition λ=532nm, 400-2000cm⁻¹

Surface elemental analysis

✓ X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy

Samples	XPS [at%]				
	C 1s	Si 2p	Al 2p	Hf 4f	C/Si ratio
SiC-HfC1	64.2	32.3	2.9	0.6	1.9
SiC-HfC2	51.0	44.0	4.0	0.9	1.2
SiC-HfC3	50.4	44.9	3.7	0.9	1.1

- XPS (NEXAS, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) operating condition : 50.0eV, 5-30scan, 400μm spot size
- Peak distribution: Pseudo-Voigt function

Crystal structure analysis

✓ High-Resolution Transmittance Electron Microscopy

- Cs-Corrected TEM (Titan ThemisZ, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) operating condition : Accel. Voltage 10.0kV, High Voltage 300kV
- Red line : Fast Fourier transformed (FFT) image and d-spacing calculation; HfC d₍₁₁₁₎=0.27
- Blue line : FFT image and d-spacing calculation; SiC d₍₁₁₁₎=0.25

Mechanical & Creep properties

✓ Bend Stress Relaxation test

Properties	SiC-HfC1	SiC-HfC2	SiC-HfC3
Tensile strength [GPa]	2.15 ± 0.22	2.34 ± 0.14	1.70 ± 0.10
Tensile modulus [GPa]	347.58 ± 30.03	344.49 ± 18.97	378.83 ± 25.92
Tensile strength after oxidation [GPa]	1.24 ± 0.27	1.45 ± 0.22	1.57 ± 0.17
Creep resistance in Ar ³ [°C]	1200	1350	1500
Creep resistance in Air ³ [°C]	< 1000	< 1000	1300

- Creep resistance : Stress relaxation parameter [m] < 0.8
- Bend stress relaxation test operating condition : graphite mold / Ar / 1 hour each temperature, R₀=8mm

Conclusion

- ✓ The polycrystalline silicon carbide – hafnium carbide nanocomposite fibers were fabricated by polymer derived ceramics (PDCs) method using aluminum, hafnium acetylacetonate modified polycarbosilane
- ✓ During the intermediate oxidation heat-treatment, the excess carbon was eliminated via reaction with oxygen up to 3.2wt%
- ✓ As removing excess carbon, high crystallinity SiC-HfC nanocomposite fiber could be fabricated at the same sintering temperature of 1800°C
- ✓ Near-stoichiometric SiC-HfC nanocomposite fiber (C/Si ratio=1.1) which a lot of removing carbon shows the highest creep & oxidation resistance. however, The RT tensile strength exhibits the lowest as a result of coarsened silicon carbide grain structure.

Reference

- [1] Dong-geun Shin, et al. *Key Eng Mater* 2005, 287, 91.
- [2] Yoonjoo Lee, et al. *Compos Res.* 30.2.102, (2017)
- [3] Seokhun Jang, et al. *Ceramics International* 46.5 (2020): 5602-5609.
- [4] Seong-Gun Bae, et al. *Ceramics International* 48.9 (2022): 13295-13303.
- [5] Seong-Gun Bae et al. *J. European Ceram. SoC* (2023): 1385-1396